

IMPACT FACTOR
0.316

By
INTERNATIONAL SOCIETY FOR
RESEARCH ACTIVITY (ISRA - JIF)
<http://www.isra-jif.org>

Volume 2

No 4

April 2017

ISSN : 2454 - 4531

AKCE QUEST

Quarterly Journal

ARULMIGU KALASALINGAM COLLEGE OF EDUCATION

(Accredited by NAAC at B Grade with a CGPA of 2.87 on a four point scale)
Krishnankoil-626 126, Srivilliputtur (Taluk), Virudhunagar District

EFFECTIVENESS OF JIGSAW METHOD ON LEARNING CHEMISTRY AMONG XI STANDARD STUDENTS

¹ Dr. N. Subramanian

Abstract

Chemistry is a logical science. The students can study the chemistry concepts in any order, but it's probably best to start from the top and work their way down, since many concepts build on understanding units, conversion and how atoms and molecules interact. Chemistry can be a tough subject to learn, especially if they aren't going about studying this complicated science the right way. This research paper is based on the study conducted to find out the effectiveness of jigsaw method on the learning chemistry of eleventh standard students. The intention of this research was also to explore the linkage between teaching technique and student learning. In this study, the measuring instrument was used an achievement test in chemistry (post-test). One lesson (Chemical Bonding) was selected from 11th class Chemistry for this study. A sample of 50 students was randomly selected from Kanna Matriculation Higher Secondary School, Puliangudi. "Pre test and post test quasi experimental design" was selected for this research study. Experimental group was taught with the help of Jigsaw Method whereas the control group was taught the same lessons through traditional method of teaching for the period of six (6) weeks. t-test was used to analyze the data.

Introduction

Cooperative learning, as the name suggests, stands for a learning process or strategy in which the students get opportunities to learn by themselves in a group in a cooperative or non-cooperative environment by forming a number of teams, each consisting of a small number of students of different levels of ability for the understanding of a subject. They share all information among themselves and help each other for having the required knowledge, understanding and application of one or the other aspects of the content material, or course units included in their syllabus. It seems quite contrary to the practice of teaching-learning prevalent in our current educational system. The cooperative learning ideology rests in making the teaching-learning process as learner centered rather than being content or teacher centered.

Jigsaw Method

In education, jigsaw is a teaching technique invented by social psychologist Elliot Aronson in 1971. Students of an average sized class (26 to 33 students) are divided into competency groups of four to six students, each of which is given a list of subtopics to research. Individual members of each group then break off to work with the "experts" from other groups, researching a part of the material being studied, after which they return to their starting group in the role of instructor for their subcategory. The jigsaw strategy is a cooperative learning technique appropriate for students from 3rd to 12th grade. It is also used extensively in adult English Second Language (or ESL) classes. The strategy is an efficient teaching method that also encourages listening, engagement, and interaction, peer teaching and cooperative by giving each member of the group an essential part to play in the academic activity. Both individual and group accountability are built into the process. The Jigsaw method is a cooperative learning technique in which students work in small groups. Jigsaw can be used in a variety of ways for a variety of goals, but it is primarily used for the acquisition and presentation of new material, review, or informed debate. In this method, each group member is assigned to become an "expert" on some aspect of a unit of study. After reading about their area of expertise, the experts from different groups meet to discuss their topic, and then return to their groups and take turns teaching their topics to their group mates.

Assistant Professor, S Veerasamy Chettiar College of Education,
Puliangudi, Tamilnadu

Learning Chemistry

Learning is a relatively permanent change in behaviour potentiality that occurs as result of reinforced practice. Learning is a process and not a product. It involve all those experience and training of an individual (right from birth) which help him to produce changes in his behaviour. Learning leads to changes in behaviour but this does not necessarily mean that these changes always bring about improvement or positive development. One has an equal chance to drift to the negative side of human personality. Chemistry is a logical science. The students can study the chemistry concepts in any order, but it's probably best to start from the top and work their way down, since many concepts build on understanding units, conversion and how atoms and molecules interact. Chemistry can be a tough subject to learn, especially if they aren't going about studying this complicated science the right way. While there are no secret shortcuts to help them master Chemistry overnight, they can make it easier by studying the right way. And also, Learning chemistry involves practice. For making effective practice in learning chemistry, jigsaw method of co-operative learning is used in this study.

Methodology

Research Design

The study adopted an untreated control group, pre test and post test quasi experimental design. *Sample:* Participants (N=50) were XI standard students studying in Kanna Matriculation School under state board syllabus for the year 2016-17.

Procedure

The present study follows the experimental methodology and participants were randomly assigned to experimental and control groups to identify effect of the independent variable (Jigsaw Method) on the dependent variable (Achievement in Chemistry).

Instrumentations

Chemistry Achievement Test: It refers to the topics cover lesson (Chemical Bonding) prescribed for XI standard Chemistry subject belong to State Board Syllabus resulted in developing 30-item chemistry achievement test measuring chemistry achievement level of XI standard students.

Significance of the Study

Jigsaw method strategies, properly structured, have proven to be efficient and effective in promoting mastery of knowledge and skills among students of all abilities and ages. Jigsaw method strategies can enhance creativity by harnessing the power of many kinds of human intelligence and providing task structures that facilitate shared work and responsibility. Jigsaw method is an instructional task design that engages students actively in achieving a lesson objective through their own efforts and the efforts of the members of their small learning team. In a good jigsaw method lesson, it is difficult to complete the assignment successfully without productive collaboration and both easier and more engaging to complete it as a team. Four features have been regularly shown to be central to the success of any jigsaw lesson. First and foremost is positive interdependence, a spirit of "all for one and one for all. The second key feature is accountability at the group and the individual level. That is, the group cannot succeed unless each member demonstrates success or significant progress. The third essential feature is what the Johnson's call "face-to-face primitive interaction" – the acts of helping each other learn. The fourth essential feature is the focus on interpersonal and small-group skills that students use in completing jigsaw method lesson. Working successfully in a turn demands particular social skills, which are best learned and practiced in the context of real tasks. Included in this arena is the student's ability to review their own skills critically with a view to improving group effectiveness. When done properly, jigsaw method not only stimulates cognition but also gives play to the multiple forms of intelligence that students bring to and shared task. In the context of their small learning team, students have a chance to identify and take advantage of each other's strengths and expand their own notions of how to approach a

challenge. Jigsaw Method uses both goal interdependence and resource interdependence to ensure interaction and communication among group members. Changing the role of the instructor from lecturing to facilitating the groups helps foster this social environment for students to learn through interaction. Using this kind of social environment, the eleventh standard students freely understand the chemistry concepts. With this back ground the present study entitled. "The Effectiveness of Jigsaw method on learning Chemistry among XI standard students" is attempted.

Objectives of the Study

1. To diagnose the problems of the learners in learning Chemistry through lecture method.
2. To find out whether there is any significant difference in the pre test scores between the control and experimental group.
3. To find out whether there is any significant difference in the post test scores between the control and experimental group.
4. To find out whether there is any significant difference in gain score between the control group and experimental group.
5. To find out the impact of jigsaw method in learning chemistry.

Hypotheses of the Study

1. There is no significant difference in the pre test scores between the control and experimental group.
2. There is no significant difference in the post test scores between the control and experimental group.
3. There is no significant difference in gain score between the control group and experimental group.
4. Jigsaw method of teaching is more effective than lecture method in learning chemistry.

Pre-test Analysis

Ho: 01 There is no significant difference in the pre test scores between the control and experimental group.

Table 1.01 t - test for the pre test scores between the control and experimental group

Group	N	Mean	SD	t - values		Remarks (5% level of significance)
				Calculated Value	Table Value	
Control	25	11.2000	2.72336	0.968	2.01	NS
Experimental	25	12.0800	3.63914			

NS - Not Significant

In the above table, the calculated 't' value (0.966) is less than the table value (2.01) for df at 0.05 level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted. It shows that there is no significant difference in the pre test scores between the control and experimental group.

Post-test Analysis

Ho: 02 There is no significant difference in the post test scores between the control and experimental group.

Table 1.02 T-test for the post test scores between the control and experimental group

Group	N	Mean	SD	T - values		Remarks (5% level of significance)
				Calculated Value	Table Value	
Control	25	26.6800	2.65707	2.602	2.01	S
Experimental	25	27.1200	2.50533			

S- Significant

In the above table, the calculated 't' value (2.602) is greater than the table value (2.01) at 0.05 level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. It shows that there is significant difference in the post test scores between the control and experimental group.

Gain Score Analysis

Ho: 03 There is no significant difference in gain score between the control group and experimental group.

Table 1.03 t- Test for the gain scores of control group and experimental group.

Group	N	Mean	S.D.	t - values		Remarks (5% level of Significance)
				Calculated Value	Table Value	
Control	25	15.0000	4.18330	2.414	2.01	S
Experimental	25	15.4400	3.27974			

S- Significant

In the above table, the calculated 't' value (2.414) is greater than the table value (2.01) for df at 49 (50-1) at 0.05 level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. It shows that there is significant difference in gain scores between the control group experimental group. The mean scores show that the experimental group scores higher than the control group in post test.

Discussion of Results

The major findings in the research work have shown that jigsaw method is an important method of teaching which affects students' achievement and interest in chemistry of XI standard students. In this study, to find out the XI standard students' performance in chemistry, an experiment was conducted on XI standard students of 2015-2016. In this study, Chemistry refers to the topics cover lesson (Chemical Bonding) prescribed for XI standard Chemistry subject belong to State Board Syllabus. The investigator had selected 50 students and divided in to two groups in from Sri Kanna Girls Higher Secondary School, Puliyangudi. These 50 students were equally and equivalently into two groups as experimental and control group. Hence each group consists of 25 students.

In the pre test, the control and experimental groups did not differ significantly in achievement test in Chemistry. In the post test, the students of Experimental group scored higher than the students of control group, experimental group scored more than the control group in post test. Regarding gain scores, the students of experimental group scored higher than the students of control group. The gain scores of experimental group was significantly higher than that of the control group.

The experimental group scored higher than the control group in the post test. This may be due to the fact that the Jigsaw method is more effective than the traditional method of teaching because the student discussed the connectional shared it with peers through this discussion. The student freely clarify their doubt with others, it reduces hesitation and it helps to reducing racial conflict and increasing positive educational out comes. It may also be due to the students learn cooperatively as group members share responsibility for each other's learning by using critical thinking and social skills, besides it helps to improve listening, communication and problem solving skills. And also the Jigsaw method is more effective in learning of Chemistry, because this method help to student's integrated knowledge and understanding from various sources and experts then also perceives the feelings and needs of others accurately and uses that information to approach them and it helps to elimination of misconception reduce students difficulties and realize meaning full learning.

Conclusion

The results of the study reveal that the concepts of chemistry have been imbibed by the students when they are learnt the concepts by jigsaw method of learning. The Jigsaw method of learning has a noticeable impact in the achievement in chemistry of XI standard students. The findings of the present study not only demonstrate that the students are satisfied with jigsaw method of learning but also

Improved their scores in the achievement of chemistry. Hence the jigsaw method of learning is one of the effective teaching strategies incorporated to improve the XI standard students' level of knowledge in chemistry. In traditional method the students are only passive learners. But the jigsaw method of learning makes the students active and provides optimum opportunities to learn and retain various chemistry concepts at XI standard level. Based on the findings of the study, it clearly shows that jigsaw method could be very appreciated by the XI standard students and stimulates an academic approach to them. No student can succeed completely unless everyone works well together as a team.

References

1. S.S.Chandra, *Modern Education*, Atlantic Publication, New Delhi (3rd Edition), 2008:3.
2. Ramesh Ghanta, *Modern Education*, Vikas Publication, New Delhi (3rd Edition), 2004:6,7.
3. S.K.Mangal, *Educational Psychology*, Prentice Hall India Publication, New Delhi (2nd Edition), 2007:2,171.
4. N.Dash, *Psychology Teaching Learning Process*, Cosmr Publication, New Delhi (2nd Edition), 2005, 1:5.
5. R.Sharma, *Educational Psychology*, Kanishka Publication, New Delhi (2nd Edition), 2007,11,12.
6. Gupta and Sharma, "Effectiveness of Cooperative Learning Approach Over Conventional Method in Mathematics at High School Level" Vol.2, No.1, Jan 2012.